

Androgen Receptor Expression in Estrogen Receptor Positive Breast Carcinoma and Correlation with Clinicopathologic Parameters

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Abstract:

Breast carcinoma is the most common malignancy and leading cause of cancer-related mortality in females. Breast carcinomas show wide variety of features. Breast tissue and breast carcinoma are highly hormone dependent. Treatment mode and prognosis depends upon expression of hormonal receptors like estrogen receptor(ER), progesterone receptor(PR) and androgen receptor(AR). Nearly 70% of breast carcinoma cases are ER positive. 60- 80% breast cancer cases are positive for AR expression. 21 ER positive breast carcinoma cases from AJ Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre, Mangalore, were analysed. Immunohistochemistry analysis was performed. 85.7% of the cases were AR positive. All grade 1 tumors were positive for AR expression and all grade 3 tumors were AR negative. 88.9% PR positive breast carcinoma cases were AR positive. All Her2 negative cases showed AR positive expression and all Her2 3+ cases were AR positive. 75% cases with less than 15% Ki67 expression and 88.2% cases with more than 15% Ki 67 expression showed AR positive expression.

In conclusion, the comparison between AR expression in ER positive breast tumors with PR, HER2 and Ki67 were not found to be statistically significant. AR positivity in 85.7% of ER positive breast carcinoma indicates a possible therapeutic role for AR antagonists. The association between AR expression in breast carcinoma and other clinicopathologic parameters were not conclusive. Further studies on larger group of patients are required for better assessment of AR expression in ER positive breast cancer.

Keywords: Breast cancer, Androgen receptor, Estrogen receptor, Progesterone receptor, Her2 expression.

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Introduction

Breast carcinoma is the most common cancer and leading cause of cancer related mortality in females (11.6% of the total cancer deaths) [1, 2]. Most of the cases of breast carcinomas are reported from economically developed countries [1].

The most important challenge that the modern world and medical science facing is the early diagnosis and effective treatment of breast cancer . Breast carcinomas show wide variety of features. Different types of breast carcinomas are presenting according to clinical, morphological, genetic, histologic and hormone receptor status. Treatment mode and prognosis depends upon primary tumor size, histologic type, grade, lymph node involvement, metastases and expression of hormonal receptors like estrogen receptor(ER), progesterone receptor(PR) and androgen receptor (AR).

Breast tissue and breast carcinoma are highly hormone dependent. Estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, androgen receptor and vitamin D receptor are nuclear receptors included

in the family of steroid receptors. Proliferation of breast cells induced by these steroid hormones. ER and PR show essential regulatory role in the pathogenesis and growth of breast cancer affecting cell proliferation and differentiation. As well as, AR shows functional and structural similarity to ER and PR. There are literature reviews which report the presence of AR in breast cancer cells. 60-80% breast cancer cases are positive for AR expression [1,13,17,20,21]. This indicates role for AR as a predictive, prognostic and therapeutic agent. According to some studies, the range for AR expression varies from low (34%) to high (91.9%). Disparity in AR expression cut off values and difference in examined populations are reasons for this wide range.

Nearly 70% of breast carcinoma cases are ER positive [2]. The objectives of this study are to assess the expression of AR in ER positive breast carcinomas and to correlate AR expression with other clinical and pathologic parameters like grade of tumor, PR, HER 2 and Ki 67 expression.

Material and Methods

The study conducted in the Central Diagnostic Laboratory of AJ Institute of medical science and research centre, Mangalore from May 2022 to August 2023. A total of 21 ER positive breast cancer cases were analysed. Biopsy specimens and resected surgical specimens from breast were included in the study. Immunohistochemistry analysis was performed on formalin fixed and paraffin embedded breast cancer tissues. Data used for analysis were derived from medical records. The following information was obtained from all patient's medical records: age, sex, site of tumour, size of tumour, type of tumour, grade of tumour, stage of tumour and PR/HER2/Ki67 status.

Immunohistochemistry Staining Procedure for AR: Sections of 3-5µm thickness were made with blocks from biopsy specimens and surgically resected specimens from the breast. These sections were incubated at 70⁰c for 20 min.

Immunohistochemistry staining done according to Pathn Situ Biotechnologies guidelines using Androgen Receptor (Clone: EP120) Rabbit Monoclonal Antibody.

The ASCO/CAP guidelines [7] was used for the interpretation of ER, PR, Ki67 and AR.

Criteria For AR Positivity: AR positivity status was determined by evaluating the intensity and percentage of AR expression by tumour cells. The grading of intensity done as negative, weak, intermediate or strong. AR expression is considered as positive when more than 10% tumour cells show intermediate or strong intensity of expression[1]. (Figure 1, 2)

Histopathology slides were examined and evaluated by pathologists by using light microscope(Olympus BX51) and results were noted down.

Figure 1: AR- positive nuclear immunohistochemical staining in invasive ductal breast carcinoma, IHC 400X

Figure 2: AR- negative nuclear immunostaining in invasive ductal carcinoma, IHC 400X

Statistics

Statistical analysis were performed using SPSS (v20) software. Comparison of categorical variables were performed by chi square test. Data were expressed as frequency and percentage for categorical variables.

Results

AR expression was tested on 21 cases of ER positive breast carcinomas. Androgen receptor expression and clinicopathological findings of these cases are given in Table 1. All the cases were between 38 to 74 years. Average age of patients was 52.71 years.(Table 1)

Table 1: AR expression and clinicopathological parameters

NO	HOSPITAL	AGE	SEX	SITE	SIZE	TYPE	GRADE	STAGE	AR	ER	PR	HER2	Ki 67	I
1	779123	68	F	RIGHT	6X4.5X3.2	IDC		2 pT4bN2aMx	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	20-30%	
2	3082/22	51	F	LEFT		IDC			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	30-35%	
3	699/23	43	F	RIGHT	0.5X0.4	IDC	3	pT1aN3a	NEGATIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	40%	
4	2641/23	61	F			IDC			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	20-25%	
5	32/23	46	F	LEFT		IDC c CRIB			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	1+	25-30%	
6	3881/22	57	F	RIGHT	5X4X3.5	ILC	2	pT3N0	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	1+	50-60%	
7	7641/23	72	F	RIGHT	8X5.8X3.5	IDC	2	pT3N0	NEGATIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	20-30%	
8	2522/23	51	F	RIGHT	3.2X2.6X2	MUCINOUS	1	pT2N0Mx	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+		
9	887/23	38	F	LEFT	3.5X3X1.2	IC	2	pT2N0Mx	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	10%	
10	6868/23	59	F	LEFT		IDC			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	>90%	
11	2315/23	60	F	LEFT	2.5X1.5X2	IDC	2	pT2N2a	NEGATIVE	W POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	2+	10%	
12	4531/22	52	F	LEFT	2.2X2.2X2	IDC	2	pT2N1a	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	NEGATIVE	3+	60-70%	
13	2729/23	44	F	RIGHT	3.5X2.5X2	IDC	2	pT2N1a	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	1+	50-60%	
14	8483/22	43	F	LEFT	9.5X6X4	DC INSITU	2	pTisNx	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	1+	10%	
15	7038/22	44	F	LEFT	2.5X2X1	MUCINOUS	1	pT2N0	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	40-50%	
16	6604/22	38	F	LEFT		IDC	1		POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	<5%	
17	7623/22	49	F	LEFT	3X1.8X1	IDC	2	pT2N1a	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	2+	20-30%	
18	1322/23	39	F	LEFT		IDC			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	50%	
19	3315/23	52	F	RIGHT					POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	3+	35-40%	
20	1927/22	74	F	RIGHT		IDC			POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	1+	30-40%	
21	1361/23	66	F	LEFT					POSITIVE	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	1+	40-50%	

AR Expression In 21 ER Positive Breast Carcinoma: Out of these 21 cases, 18 cases (85.7%) were positive and 3 cases (14.3%) were negative for AR expression.(Table 2)

Table 2: AR expression in 21 ER positive breast carcinoma

AR			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Positive	18	85.7
	Negative	3	14.3
	Total	21	100.0

Grade of Tumour And AR Expression: All three grade 1 tumours (100%) were positive for AR expression. Seven out of nine cases (77.8%) of grade 2 tumours were AR positive and 2 cases (22.2%) of grade 2 tumours were AR negative. All grade 3 tumours (1 case) were AR negative.(Figure 3)

Figure 3: AR expression and grade of tumor

AR Expression In PR Positive And PR Negative Breast Carcinoma: Sixteen out of eighteen (88.9%) PR positive breast carcinomas are AR positive and two out of three cases of PR negative breast carcinomas are AR positive. (Table 3)

Table 3: AR expression and PR expression

			AR		Total	P value
			Positive	Negative		
PR	Positive	Count	16	2	18	0.386
		% within PR	88.9%	11.1%	100.0%	
	Negative	Count	2	1	3	
		% within PR	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%	
Total	Count	18	3	21		
	% within PR	85.7%	14.3%	100.0%		

HER2 Expression And AR Expression: All the sixcases (28.6%) with HER2 negative expression showed AR positive expression. Eight cases (38.1%) showed 2+ HER2 expression. Five out of eight cases (62.5%) with HER2 2+

expression were AR positive and remaining 3 cases (37.5%) were AR negative.

All HER2 3+ cases (33.3%) were AR positive. (Table 4).

Table 4: AR Expression and HER2 Expression

			AR		Total	P VALUE
			POSITIVE	NEGATIVE		
HER2	1+	Count	6	0	6	0.58
		% within HER2	100.0%	.0%	100.0%	
		% within AR	33.3%	.0%	28.6%	
	2+	Count	5	3	8	
		% within HER2	62.5%	37.5%	100.0%	
		% within AR	27.8%	100.0%	38.1%	
	3+	Count	7	0	7	
		% within HER2	100.0%	.0%	100.0%	
		% within AR	38.9%	.0%	33.3%	
Total	Count	18	3	21		
	% within HER2	85.7%	14.3%	100.0%		
	% within AR	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

KI 67 Expression And AR Expression: Three out of four cases (75%) with less than 15% Ki67 expression showed AR positive expression and one case (25%) showed AR negative expression. Out f 17 cases with more than 15% Ki 67 expression, 15 cases (88.2%) showed AR positive expression and 2 cases (11.8%) showed AR negative expression.(Table 5)

Table 5- AR expression and Ki 67

			AR		Total	P Value
			Positive	Negative		
ki 67 CATE-GORY	<15 %	Count	3	1	4	0.489
		% within ki 67 CATE-GORY	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%	
		% within AR	16.7%	33.3%	19.0%	
	>15 %	Count	15	2	17	
		% within ki 67 CATE-GORY	88.2%	11.8%	100.0%	
		% within AR	83.3%	66.7%	81.0%	
Total	Count	18	3	21		
	% within ki 67 CATE-GORY	85.7%	14.3%	100.0%		
	% within AR	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

Discussion

Androgen signalling is involved in normal breast cell differentiation and growth [6,7]. Szelei et al described how androgen signalling take part in maintaining cellular balance. There are three mechanisms to control cellular balance: proliferation stimulation, proliferation inhibition and apoptosis inhibition [8]. Importance of AR in homeostasis of normal breast tissue and how it maintain balance between proliferative effect of ER and proliferation inhibition are described by Yu et al [9]. The proposed mechanisms for explaining how androgen influence risk of tumour growth and development of breast carcinoma are: 1) by binding to AR (directly stimulating malignant cell proliferation), 2) by binding directly to ER (competitive inhibition of 17 beta estradiol stimulatory effect on neoplastic cells), 3) by conversion to estradiol [10]. Different hormonal factors (interactions with ER) and extra hormonal factors (eg: extracellular MAP-kinase activity) also influence the clinical effects of AR [11].

Activated AR can competitively bind with estrogen responsive elements and can antagonize the transcription activity of ER (26). This reveals the functioning of AR as tumor suppressor in ER positive breast cancers. Thus ER positive breast carcinoma with AR positive status have a better prognosis as compared to AR negative carcinoma [13]. Studies done by Elebro K et al and Hu R et al conclude that tumors with both AR and ER expression are associated with a better outcome.

Reported cases and published data show AR expression positively associated with ER and PR expression [8,12,13,14,15,16]. Some other reports show negative correlation. There are studies which show that there is no correlation between AR expression and other hormonal parameters like ER and PR [17].

A correlation between AR and Her2 expression has not been conclusively established [9,12].

According to literature there is association between AR expression and lower histologic grade [12,14,15,16,18]. However, Gonzalez LO et al says that there is no significant correlation between AR expression and histologic grade [17].

Other studies differs in that describe independent association between clinical parameters and AR expression [8,17].

Ogawa et al concluded that AR expression is associated with lower tumour size, lower incidence of distant metastases and lymph node involvement. Yu Q, Gonzalez LO, Miller WL et al have discussed negative correlation between these parameters [9,12,17,19].

Conclusion

The present study reveals that all grade 1 ER positive tumors are AR positive and all grade 3 ER positive tumors are AR negative. This may not show statistical significance due to less number of cases. The comparison between AR expression in ER positive breast tumors with PR, HER2 and Ki67 were not found to be statistically significant.

Breast carcinomas with AR expression are treated by natural and synthetic androgens^(22,23,24). According to the present study, AR positivity in 85.7% of ER positive breast carcinoma indicates a possible therapeutic role for AR antagonists. Studies revealed that selective AR modulators can reduce the tumor weight by 90%. They can also solve tumor induced cachexia in one month⁽²⁵⁾.

The association between AR expression in breast carcinoma and other clinicopathologic parameters were not conclusive. Further studies on larger group of patients are required for better assessment of AR expression in ER positive breast cancer.

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